

DEGRADATION SMC UNDER HOT WATER IMMERSION

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Abstract:

With the development of material science and technology, more and more fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) is used in modern society and it provides lots of convenient to daily life. Productions with excellent performance but low cost are popular for consumers and producer. As increasing of service lives, durability of FRP is essential properties which deeply affects structural design and serve lives. Hot water immersion degradation is a common and no negligible factor on durability of composite materials.

Due to its high productive, low cost and excellent properties, sheet molding compound (SMC) is widely used in many areas, including automobiles, aerospace, electronics, defense, energy recreational and home-related industries. The material is produced by releasing long strands of chopped glass fibers onto a layer with unsaturated resin. SMC is often used in complex applications, to provide corrosion resistance, and for structural parts in low cost, high volume programs.

At current study, panels were cut from bath tab which was molded from SMC sheets consisted of 25mm-length glass fiber, unsaturated polyester and other filler along two directions including deep and width ways. Before cutting action the bath tab should pour into hot water at 90 degree from 0h, 250h, 500h, 750h, 1000h, 1250h, and 1500h. Samples were prepared with size 115mm×15mm×3.8mm and different immersion time, different fiber orientation. Then bending and acoustic emission test was carried out to do more deep investigation on the initial fracture and mechanical property.

1. Introduction

SMC (sheet molding compound) is well known as the forming method through compression molding as a mass production-oriented material [1-2]. The standard of the molding time of cure is 1 minute/mm in thickness, therefore it is considered as one of the most convenient molding methods of composite. As shown in Fig.1, material is layered in a metallic mold. Heating and compression is applied to melt resin. The final products were heat curing.

Fig.1. Glass SMC in the study

However, there still have some problems. The relationship between the changes of glass fiber's orientation and mechanical properties was not clarified. Additionally, predicting of the long-term physical properties in water environment is unsolved. Therefore, in this study, the plates were cut from the actual bathtub and the mechanical properties were compared with the glass fibers directions of flowing. Moreover, the 0, 250, 500, 750, 1000, 1500 hours 90 degree hot water immersion experiment was conducted and changing of physical and mechanical properties was investigated. Initial fracture stress and AE measurement were obtained and was proposed as an allowable products design.

Acoustic emission (AE) technique has been developed over the last two decades as a non-destructive evaluation technique and as a useful tool for material research [3]. AE is an efficient method to monitor in real time, damage growth in both structural components and laboratory specimens. In loaded materials, the strain-energy release due to

microstructural changes results in stress-wave propagation. In the case of composite materials, many mechanisms have been confirmed as AE sources including matrix cracking, fiber - matrix interface deboning, fiber fracture and delamination [4]. AE deals with the detection of such waves at the materials surface. Therefore, this technique potentially allows not only the location of the source of the emission, but also the determination of its nature. Nevertheless, the use of such techniques needs a clear understanding of relationships between the recorded signal and the damage process. However the stress waves resulting from the microstructural changes depend on the propagation conditions including attenuation, damping and boundary surface interactions. So the signal delivered by the sensor is a strongly modified representation of the original source. Nevertheless, it is realistic to consider that this signal contains some features representation of the source in such a manner that direct correlation exists between the damage mechanisms and the magnitude of the various AE parameters. Consequently, each signal can be considered as the acoustic signature of the different damage modes.

Many authors have already worked in this field. Barre and Benzeggagh [5], testing glass fiber reinforced polypropylene samples, reported that the acoustic signal amplitude varies with the corresponding damage mode: AE amplitude range from 40 to 55 dB corresponds to matrix cracking, 60 - 65 dB to debonding, 65 - 85 dB to pull-out and 85 - 95 dB to fiber fracture. Ely and Hill showed that when fiber breaks and longitudinal splitting occurs at the same location in unidirectional graphite/epoxy specimen, the stronger signals (high amplitude, energy, counts and long duration) resulted from fiber breakage and the weaker ones (low amplitude, energy, counts and short duration) resulted from longitudinal split. Suziki et al. [6] observed the following correlation between failure mechanisms and AE frequency in glass/polyester composite: matrix cracking (30 - 150 kHz), fiber debonding and pull-out (180 - 290 kHz), fiber breaking (300 - 400 kHz). Uenoya [7] proposed a rising-slope criterion to discriminate AE source mechanisms in laminated composites (glass-fiber-fabric/epoxy). Barnes and Ramirez [8], testing carbon fiber reinforced pipes, used correlation plots of event amplitude and duration time to characterize the different modes of failure. They reported that high duration-low/intermediate amplitude (45 - 70 dB) events are

associated with delamination and debonding while high amplitude-high duration events are associated with fiber fracture.

However, a single damage mechanism such as matrix cracking can produce a wide range of AE signal parameters [9]. For the various mechanisms, overlap of the AE parameters distributions results from signal attenuation, closely occurring emissions from different sources, equipment setting and large data sets. Thus, multiparameter analysis using many AE waveform parameters should be necessary to improve the identification of damage modes. Pattern recognition has been proposed as a suitable multivariable technique for the classification of AE events [10]. If supervised pattern recognition is used, the number of damage mechanisms must be known in advance. The term unsupervised pattern recognition is used to describe the complete methodology consisting of procedures for descriptors selection, cluster analysis and cluster validity. Ono and Huang [11] proposed a distinction between several damage mechanisms with waveform-based analyses associated to advanced pattern recognition techniques. They identified six different types of damage in carbon fiber and glass fiber composites subjected to tensile loading in different configurations.

In this paper, the glass fiber SMC used for bathtub were fabricated and investigated the initial fracture and mechanical properties of samples and how the fibers orientation influences the crack development. AE data with the stress was investigated and trying to find what the relationship between the yield point and initial fracture in the bending test. With the crack development, what damage in the samples occurred that also was observed.

2. Materials and Experiment

Bathtubs which mainly have 22wt% glass fibers with 1cm length and unsaturated polyester resin were molded by SMC, for hot water immersions, 90 degree water was put into these bathtubs for 0, 250, 500, 750, 1000, 1250, and 1500h. Then the panels which were distinguished by different hours cut from each bathtub. As shown in Fig.2, the final samples were cut from these panels, its length was 115mm, width was 15mm, and thickness was 3.8mm, respectively. The specimens were prepared in two directions including Y (flowing direction) and X (perpendicular to Y direction), and different hot

water immersed time. The “S” in the sample’s name means the single side immersion.

In consideration of bending is more closed to the real environment. Acoustic emission (AE) technique has been developed over the last two decades as a useful tool for material research. Therefore, bending with AE test was used as researching method. For the testing, the mode pattern as shown in Fig.3, it was carried out under 1mm/min with a 60.8mm support distance. In order to imitate the real loading environment, the immersion side was putting in upward.

In order to discuss the fracture behavior, AE signals were monitored by PCI-2-PAC series AE instrument. Here the type of AE transducers with resonant frequencies at 75/ [-150] kHz. The sensor output was amplified by 40dB at preamplifier and the threshold was set as 42dB. After the installation of the transducers, a pencil lead break [12] procedure was used to simulate AE signals in the calibration of each test. According to the previous studies the AE measured by 140 kHz is possible to discuss the interface between glass fiber and matrix or the fracture of resin while 1MHz is for the fracture of glass fiber.

Fig.2 .Y and X specimens position in the panel

Fig.3. Bending specimen with sensor installed in the three-point bending equipment
(Span length: 60.8mm R15- α SERIES SENSOR
Operating frequency range (kHz): 50-200)

3. Result and discussion

3.1 Fracture morphology of the bending tested specimens

The tested Y specimens after bending test from side view can be observed several layers of SMC as shown in Fig.4. In particularly, the crack propagated along the lamination partly. It is considered related to the molding method of bath plated molded by SMC. The compounded unsaturated polyester was covered by the filling down cut glass fibers, and then covered another compounded resin consequently with the glass fibers layer as the core of sandwich. Although the resin impregnated into the glass fiber layer, the skin layer of the sandwich is still resin reach area. Therefore SMC piece is suitable to be considered have such three layer’s structure of resin-glass fiber/resin-resin. The crack might generate in the resin reach layer and then propagated along layers to form such laminate cracks.

Fig.4 .Y specimens side view after bending test

On the other hand, unlike Y samples, X samples’ crack developed in a vertical orientation. In the sample models, as show in Fig.5, the fiber arrangement inside the sample is completely different between these two types’ samples which led to different fracture behaviors. Inside the X samples the glass fibers vertical to its’ longitudinal direction, so during bending process the crack should develop between each fibers in a vertical state. But for Y samples, the fibers arrange parallel to longitudinal direction, when bending going on, the crack should develop along the fiber surface that looks like zig-zag in side view.

Fig.5 .Photos and schematic and illustration Y and X sample’s models

Additionally, compare individual Y and X samples amplitude-time distribution diagram, the typical phenomenon were observed as showed in the Fig.6 and Fig.7. The Y samples hits increasing little by little. But the X samples hits increasing rapidly in one position. Because in the X samples, the crack formed at once, but the crack in Y samples formed step by step.

Fig.6 .One X sample amplitude-time distribution diagram (Increasing Rapidly)

Fig.7 .One Y sample amplitude-time distribution diagram (Increasing little by little)

3.2 Initial fracture during three-point bending test

Although there are many kinds of fracture of FRP, it is considered that the initiate fracture during the bending test is critical. In details, it is considered helpful to decide the design tolerance stress of material by investigate the initiate fracture. In tensile test, the initial fracture can be observed in stress-

strain curve. But that it is difficult to use stain stage in the bending specimen, that is to say it cannot obtain the stress-strain curve. Therefore, at current study, AE method is used to determine the initial fracture stress for bending test. The point where AE counts increasing rapidly were checked its possibility of finding the initial fracture. The evolution of the stress and the cumulative number of AE counts during bending test of the sample versus the time were shown in Fig.8. The cumulative AE counts are a global measure which enables the estimation of the damage degree during loading. After the first silence, a noticeable increase in AE activity is detected around 44s. Then the emission increases significantly until the final rupture. After an initiation period, the number of AE counts increased approximately linearly with time at stress higher than 31.8MPa. So point about 44s with a bending stress of 31.8 MPa is considered relative to initial fracture. And the initial fracture distribution are given in the Fig 9(a), (b)

Fig.8 . A sample to explain the method to find the initial fracture

Fig.9 (a) X samples initial fracture distribution

Fig.9 (b) Y samples initial fracture distribution

3.3 Mechanical property

Here, the specimens under 0 and 1500 hours hot water immersion were used as samples to discuss the effect of the hot water on the mechanical property of glass fiber SMC. The modulus, strength distribution were summarized in Fig.10(a), (b), (c), (d) respectively.

Fig.10 (a) Bending Modulus-Immersion Time curve of X specimens

Fig.10 (b) Bending Modulus-Immersion Time curve of Y specimens

Fig.10 (c) Bending strength-Immersion Time curve of X specimens

Fig.10 (d) Bending strength-Immersion Time curve of Y specimens

It is interesting that the hot water immersion seemed not significant influence on the X specimens because of the relative stable values both in bending modulus and strength. On the other hand it is found that the strength in bending load was decreased after 1500 hot water immersion for Y specimens. The decreasing of samples strength belongs to the water destroys the structure of these composites. While the

modulus were observed remain the same or a little increase.

Additionally, compared to X specimens, Y specimens have higher strength. It is shown in Fig 11. It is considered that the fiber orientation in Y specimens lead to the high mechanical property. That is to say different fiber orientation and mechanical property between perpendicular and horizontal are occurred due to the fiber flowing during molding.

Fig.11. Max Bending Stress-Orientation histogram

Through the beginning of bending test to the final rupture, a typical distribution of peak amplitude is given in Fig.12. It shows values in the range 43–98 dB, which means in every minute the hit can reach how large it can. After the first silence phase of the tests (before the AE counts generated) all these hits can separate to 4 types.

Fig.12. one sample peak amplitude distribution

The first one like the Fig.13 (a) showed. It happened at the beginning of loading (the first silence at the Stress-AE counts-Time curve which shown in Fig.8.) The signal of low amplitudes (42–50 dB) and short duration. It has 11.57% in all AE hits. These signals come with the dynamic breaking phenomena. So, they are considered not big attribution to the damaging material response.

The second one like the Fig.13 (b) showed. It happened at the initial fracture of loading (around the emission increases significantly point) .The signal of low- medium amplitudes (50-70 dB) and short duration. It has 70.19% in all AE hits. Of course, due to it show time these signals cannot be associated to any other mechanism than the growth of vacuoles inside the resin; in other words, to matrix micro-crack formation or fiber/matrix decohesion.

The third one like Fig.13 (c) showed. Signals with high amplitudes (>70dB), high energies. It has 18.24% in all AE hits. Because the fiber may as main mechanical provider in composites, so it always has higher strength than the matrix. That’s why we consider it to fiber rapture

The fourth one like Fig.13 (d) showed. Signal with very high duration. In composites materials no matter matrix rapture, fiber broken or fiber-matrix debonding it will not have very long duration. The only chance for this phenomenon is the fiber slipping in the matrix. When fiber slipping in the matrix, it have chance that the friction larger than the fiber strength which make the fiber broken, that is why it have high amplitude.

Fig.13 (a) one sample hit (type 1)

Fig.13 (b) one sample hit (type2)

Fig.13 (c) One sample hit (type 3)

Fig.13 (d) One sample hit (type 4)

3. Conclusions

At current study, the glass fiber SMC used for bathtub were fabricated and investigated their fiber

orientation, fiber flowing and the initial fracture measured by bending test with AE technology.

First of all, through the experiment, the different crack types were observed between the X and Y samples. That is to say X samples' crack developed in a vertical orientation. But the Y samples have both the horizontal direction and the vertical direction which is shown in Fig.5 (The red line). The fiber arrangement in the composites is the reasons for this phenomenon. Because these two different structures, X samples are more likely to describe how well the resin bonding with fibers. And also can give researchers a good method to observe the crack interface.

Additionally, strength in bending load of Y specimen was decreased after 1500h hot water immersion. It does easy explain belong to the water destroy the composites. And compared to X samples, Y samples have higher bending strength and modulus. It is considered that the fiber orientation in Y specimens lead to the high mechanical property. It is found that different fiber orientation and mechanical property between perpendicular and horizontal are occurred due to the fiber flowing during molding. But the modulus were observed remain the same or a little increase at both Y and X samples. Deeply the Y samples strength and modulus have larger discreteness than the X samples. When come to the Fig.4, it easy to observe that the crack in X samples develop besides the fiber, which means it doesn't break fiber. So the strength and modulus in each sample should remain the same. But the crack in Y samples can develop through the fibers by chance, so the strength and the modulus have large discreteness. It depend whether crack go through the fiber and how many fibers it go through.

Moreover the growth of matrix cracks and the coalescence of matrix cracks appear to create AE events having low amplitude, slowly rising and decaying. On the contrary, the interface debonding and fiber fracture leads to signals with higher amplitude, quickly rising and decaying. With loading process what damage in the composites can clearly observed from the AE data. For tensile testing, the yield point is the important parameter for the composites mechanical properties. But bending test is very difficult to find yield point through stress-strain curve. That is why the experiment adopts the AE in the experiment. The final results show that the bending yield point can be characterized by the initial fracture tress that observed from stress-time-hits curve.

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